

Analysis of the academic impact associated with the altmetrics of Ig Nobel Prize

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Introduction

The Ig Nobel Prize, based on the core concepts of science and humor, is an academic award characterized by popular science. Compared with traditional citation indicators, altmetrics use social media as the primary subject of analysis. Altmetrics data come from a variety of sources—including mainstream media, social media, blogs, and website forums—and facilitate the observation of the various aspects of academic impacts. Altmetrics may complement conventional academic evaluation methods by analyzing the academic impacts exerted by researchers through informal channels of communication.

This in turn provides alternative answers to questions concerning the numbers of reads and citations, amount of news coverage, and social policy impact of academic articles (Priem & Taraborelli, 2012; Bornmann, 2014; Thelwall, 2020). The coexistence of humor and science that characterizes the Ig Nobel Prize prompts people to consider it an amateur award and to overlook the value of winning articles on the basis of the belief that such articles lack sufficient authority. Consequently, their academic impacts are underestimated. With this idea in mind, this study explored the academic impact of Ig Nobel Prize-winning articles in medicine and physics during 2000–2020 from the perspective of Altmetrics.

Methods

This study focused on articles that won the Ig Nobel Prize between 2000 and 2020 in the fields of medicine and physics and were officially published and archived in the Scopus database. Data were collected from five indicators of PlumX Metrics, namely citations, usage, captures, mentions, and social media. Owing to the rapid updating of Altmetrics indicators in recent years and the lack of retrospective indicator data, this study used data collected in December 2022.

Research Results

As indicated in Tables 1 and 2, the award-winning articles exhibited the best performance in the usage indicator, followed by the social media. By contrast, they performed most poorly in the mention indicator. In addition, the standard deviation of the indicators indicated a high level of dispersion among the articles.

Table 1. Performance of Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical articles in five indicators of PlumX Metrics.

Medicine Prize (n = 29)	citation	usage	capture	mention	social media
Total	3,173	280,305	7,978	974	20,127
Mean	109.4	9665.6	275.1	33.5	694.1
SD	368.2	37126.6	604.7	78.8	1139.5
Max	1	8	1	0	3
Min	2,036	198,228	3,194	434	4,840
Median	24	238	84	12	196

Table 2. Performance of Ig Nobel Prize-winning physics articles in five indicators of PlumX Metrics.

Physics Prize (n = 20)	citation	usage	capture	mention	social media
Total	2,426	323,607	4,587	328	8,921
Mean	121.3	16180.3	229.3	16.4	446.1
SD	221.1	68444.8	190.1	17.9	940.5
Max	989	314,490	800	69	3,495
Min	1	0	21	1	0
Median	55	137	176.5	9	70.5

Because the value of each indicator was affected by the data source, further analysis was conducted on the sources and composition proportions of the usage and social media indicators. The sources of the usage indicator data included full-text views, abstract views, and link-outs for all Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical and physics articles on EBSCO; views and downloads of Figshare; full-text views from PLoS and PMC; and clicks of Bitly.

Table 3 shows that the sources of usage indicator data for Medicine Prize-winning articles were more strongly attributed to the numbers of full-text and abstract views and more weakly attributed to the numbers of link-outs, downloads, and clicks.

Table 3. Distribution of sources of the usage indicator for Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical articles.

Sources of usage indicator data		Number of articles (%)	Total	Mean
full text views	EBSCO	29 (100)	8,598	296.4
	PLoS	2 (7)	203,612	7021.1
	PMC	2 (7)	42,254	1457.1
abstract views	EBSCO	27 (93)	20,142	694.5
	Figshare	6 (21)	2,146	74
link-outs	EBSCO	10 (34)	1,585	54.6
downloads	Figshare	2 (7)	1,941	66.9
clicks	Bitly	2 (7)	27	0.9

Table 4 shows that the sources of usage indicator data for Physics Prize-winning articles were primarily attributed to the numbers of full-text and abstract views. In addition, only one paper had usage indicator data from all sources. This finding indicated the presence of a substantial difference in the degree of use between the sources of award-winning articles. Only few articles demonstrated exceptions.

Table 4. Distribution of data sources for the usage indicator of Ig Nobel Prize-winning physics articles.

Sources of usage indicator data		Number of articles (%)	Total	Mean
full text views	EBSCO	18 (90)	2,092	104.6
	PLoS	1 (5)	309,132	15456.6
	PMC	1 (5)	2,689	134.4
abstract views	EBSCO	16 (80)	7,166	358.3
	Figshare	1 (5)	2,039	101.9
link-outs	EBSCO	7 (35)	156	7.8
downloads	Figshare	1 (5)	293	14.6
clicks	Bitly	1 (5)	10	0.5

The sources of social media indicator data for Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical and physics articles included the numbers of likes, shares, and comments on Facebook; the numbers of tweets and retweets on Twitter; and the number of shares on Figshare.

Table 5 shows that Medicine Prize-winning articles were primarily mentioned on Twitter and Facebook, whereas Physics Prize-winning articles were mentioned more frequently on Twitter; only few articles were shared on Figshare. Accordingly, substantial differences appeared to exist in the distribution of data sources for the award-winning articles.

Table 5. Distribution of data sources for the social media indicator of Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical and physics articles.

Sources of social media indicator data		Number of articles (%)	Total	Mean	SD
Medicine Prize (n = 29)	Facebook	25 (86)	13,549	467.2	776.4
	Twitter	29 (100)	6,576	226.7	685.5
	Figshare	2 (7)	2	0.06	0.25
Physics Prize (n = 20)	Facebook	18 (90)	6,370	318.5	702.1
	Twitter	9 (45)	2,221	111.1	240.9
	Figshare	1 (5)	330	16.5	71.92

Discussion

According to the results of this study, although the degree of use in each source differed considerably among the Ig Nobel Prize-winning medical and physics articles, “views” was observed to be the main type of paper usage. In addition, articles in academic databases were used more frequently than were those from other sources. According to their performance in relation to the social media indicator, award-winning articles received the most attention on Facebook and Twitter; this finding implied relatively high visibility or spread among such articles.

References

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